

WORKING TOGETHER AND LEARNING TOGETHER:

Advancing knowledge, policy and practice with older adults across health, care and support

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WHAT'S YOUR BEEF

LOOK OUT FOR OUR SPECIALS

BURGERS

SOCKS

... (text is small and partially obscured)

FoodHall

HEALTHY FOOD DRINKS - BAKERY & MORE

... (menu items and prices)

**PAAR-net COST ACTION (CA22167)
White Paper Working Group 1 (WG1):
Health, Care and Support**

**WORKING TOGETHER
AND LEARNING TOGETHER:
ADVANCING KNOWLEDGE, POLICY
AND PRACTICE WITH OLDER ADULTS
ACROSS HEALTH, CARE
AND SUPPORT**

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Co-Authors:

- Diane **Seddon** (Bangor University – Wales)
- Tereza **Menšíková** (Masaryk University – Czechia)
- Isabelle **Tournier** (Univ Paul Valery Montpellier 3 – France)
- Bojana **Matejić** (University Of Belgrade – Serbia)
- Sebahat **Gözüm** (Akdeniz University – Türkiye)
- Ayşegül **Ilgaz** (Akdeniz University – Türkiye)
- Charlotte **Gruber** (arbeit plus Steiermark – Verein Safrangarten – Austria)
- Magda **Jordao** (Leeds Beckett University – United Kingdom)
- Kinga **Kimic** (Warsaw University of Life Sciences-SGGW – Poland)
- Abdallah **Abudayya** (VID Specialized university – Norway)
- Steven **Byrne** (University of Limerick – Ireland)
- Tamar **Yellon** (The Hebrew University of Jerusalem – Israel)
- Figen **Cavusoglu** (Ondokuz Mayıs University – Türkiye)
- Özge Öz **Yildirim** (Ondokuz Mayıs University – Türkiye)
- Ortenca **Kotherja** (Aleksander Xhuvani University – Albania)
- Nurten **Ozen** (Istanbul University – Türkiye)
- Ayla **Hendekci** (Giresun University – Türkiye)
- Henrique **Salmazo da Silva** (Catholic University of Brasilia – Brazil)
- Büşra Nur **Temür** (Akdeniz University – Türkiye)
- Ieva **Stončkaitė** (Universitat Pompeu Fabra – Spain)
- Sara **Marsillas** (Fundacion Instituto Gerontologico Matia – Spain)
- Heidi **Kaspar** (BFH Bern University of Applied Sciences – Switzerland)
- Ľubica **Vol'anská** (IESA, Slovak Academy of Sciences - Slovakia)
- Anne **Griffin** (University of Limerick – Ireland)
- Lucimere **Bohn** (University of Porto – Portugal)
- Erhan **Dag** (Kutahya University of Health Sciences –Türkiye)
- Sandra **Staudacher** (University of Basel – Switzerland)
- Meiko **Makita** (University of Dundee – United Kingdom)
- Odelyah **Saad** (Lev Academic Center – Israel)
- Nuray Bayar **Muluk** (Kirikkale University – Türkiye)

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Executive summary

This White Paper presents PAAR-NET WG1 vision of older adults as co-creators and active contributors who bring their own perspective(s) and experiences about treatment, care and support. We focus on peoples' *strengths* and *expertise*, rather than on medical conditions, frailty, and other potential limiters.

Our work across a broad range of health, care and support areas is informed by a commitment to harnessing the expertise in our local networks to overcome barriers and challenges to participation and involvement and nurture effective co-creative ways of researching and working together.

The White Paper:

- Explores key concepts underpinning participatory approaches with older adults in health, care, and support settings.
- Identifies the challenges and the opportunities of *working together* and *learning together* with older adults.
- Showcases different co-creation activities with older adults from 14 countries.
- Presents three different case studies implementing participatory approaches in research.
- Emphasises conclusions and recommendations for future co-creation activities with older adults.

Challenges

Key challenges include:

- Nomenclature with diverse cultural meanings, challenging language stereotypes, and implementing language and cultural inclusivity.
- Ensuring meaningful involvement, considering intersectionality, re-thinking traditional transactional approaches and addressing power imbalances.
- Overcoming structural barriers, resource constraints, and addressing limitations in practices such as poor-quality reporting, tokenism and box-ticking.
- Reporting and reflecting on participatory approaches across health, care and support settings and creating learning opportunities *across countries*.

Opportunities

Key opportunities include:

- Older adults are not a homogenous group – they encompass a broad spectrum of diverse abilities, experiences, backgrounds, and needs, which must be considered and included.
- The development of national standards and toolkits to underpin the quality and consistency of participatory approaches to *working with and learning from* older adults.
- The emergence of alternative and inclusive approaches and methods highlighting nuances among older adults' experiences.
- Co-creating training and skills development programmes for researchers, older adults, practitioners, and stakeholders alike, and building network programmes that bring them together.

Implications

Key implications include:

- Participatory approaches must be embedded into research training, as meaningfully engaging with older adults, and co-creating research and practice development takes skill.
- Funding and support for participatory research and practice development with older adults must be increased to inclusively translate the older co-creators' voices into practice.
- Providing opportunities for older adults to meet with one another and share their living experiences, is essential.
- Evidencing participatory activities with older adults more effectively in published outputs, and being explicit about the difference participation has made, is important in going forward.

The focus of Working Group One aligns with ethos of PAAR-Net to engage in research that:

- Harnesses living experience to promote better futures for older adults.
- Addresses social exclusion, economic disadvantage, ineffective responses to ill health, and other factors that traditionally impact older adulthood.
- Informs more inclusive policy and practice development.

By working together and learning together with older adults we can take action together across health, care and support settings.

1

INTRODUCTION

Older adults are the fastest growing population across Europe. In 2022, UNFPA EECA reported that one in five Europeans were aged 65 years or older, and they predicted that by 2100 more than 30% of the European Union population will be aged 65 or over (Vallese, 2022). Whilst ageing and longevity are to be celebrated, this demographic shift has significant implications and pose challenges for many sectors, including health, care and support.

Age is critical in understanding how people frame their well-being, health, motivation, social participation, and life experiences. We address ageing as a process that occurs throughout life, with the concept of age depending on the social structure and the meanings given to it (Calasanti and King, 2015; Johfre and Saperstein, 2023). From this perspective, the experience of ageing among older adults is profoundly heterogeneous, shaped by a multitude of factors including genetics, lifestyle, socioeconomic status, culture, and the environment. Some of these factors are social determinants of health, which contribute to unfair and avoidable health differences (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2024). The diversity in ageing experiences underscores the importance of recognizing and addressing the individual life experiences, circumstances, and needs of older adults.

Older adults have a wealth of living experiences, and they have good knowledge of how health, care and support systems work or do not work. They bring their own perspective(s) about treatment, care and support and their own experiences of engaging with health and allied care professionals. It is essential that their expertise and unique living experiences are reflected in research, policy, and practice development alongside the expertise of researchers, practitioners and policymakers.

Research plays a key role in advancing knowledge about ageing, the causes and impacts of ill-health and health inequalities, and in driving forward innovations in treatment, care and support for older adults. Research helps us to address key global health, care and support challenges *together*, and it helps us to understand:

- ➔ Which topics are important to older adults and what treatment, care and support older adults may need to help them to achieve these outcomes.
- ➔ What treatments, care and support are most effective in the short, medium, and longer term and how these can best be delivered across a range of health, care and support settings.

Researching *together* with older adults ensures that research about health, care and support addresses the questions that are most important to older adults themselves, rather than those prioritised by researchers and research funding organisations (Seddon et al., 2023).

In recent years there has been a growing commitment from the research and scientific community to actively engage with and involve older adults who have health, care and support needs in research and to realise the European vision of *science for the people, by the people* (Horizon EU magazine, April 2022). This is mirrored by the heightened policy commitment, across Europe, to co-production and to ensuring people with care and support needs have greater voice and control over their lives (Welsh Government, 2018; EU, 2023).

As an increasing political and policy priority across the world, it is now widely accepted that:

- Older adults have a right to be meaningfully involved in research that affects them on the level of research agendas, directions, dissemination, and knowledge utilisation.
- As potential research beneficiaries, older adults should have the fullest possible involvement in research, policy and practice development *if they wish*.

Stephens and Staniszewska (2015) maintain that the collaboration between individuals with care and support needs and researchers is paramount, stating that it represents a „fundamental paradigm shift in health and social care research, away from paternalism towards partnership” (2015: 2). It is recognised that co-creative and participatory approaches can help to strengthen the relevance, significance and reach of research about health, care and support (Malm et al., 2021; National Institute for Health Research, 2021), they can lead to synergistic relationships that benefit everyone, and ultimately support improvements in policy and practice (Seddon et al., 2023; Urbaniak and Wanka, 2024).

Participatory approaches also have the potential to contribute to advancing more inclusive, living-experience research that informs **creative policy designs and practical support**. Global health, care and support policies underscore the importance of healthy ageing (WHO, 2020) and independence (White House Conference for Ageing, 2015; Whitty, 2023), focusing on maintaining and promoting functional ability. The WHO defines functional ability based on individual capacity, the environmental influence(s) and their interaction (WHO, 2020).

Functional ability does not depend on the absence of disease. It is explicitly recognized to depend on socio-economic inequities, and other environmental factors (WHO, 2020). This contrasts with previous conceptualizations of healthy ageing focused mostly on avoiding disability and disease which were regarded as unrealistic and ableist (Burton et al., 2024). When older adults themselves are asked to define successful ageing, their focus is not on avoiding changes in health or cognition, but on accepting those changes while maintaining social, cognitive and physical engagement with adequate and appropriate support from the environment (Burton et al., 2024). Social engagement is particularly important, a pattern that is observed across cultures (Reich et al., 2020). In this regard, programmes based on the concept of „Age Friendly Cities and Communities” fostering diversity, inclusion, cohesion, and participation across all ages and capacities, have been internationally promoted by the WHO (2018). Since participatory approaches have engagement at their core, they can provide essential support to realise global healthy ageing goals.

Participatory approaches can facilitate reciprocal learning. In doing so, they help to challenge ageist assumptions, practices, and attitudes towards older adults (Birt et al., 2021) and help to dispute stigmatising narratives about older adults’ physical and mental capacities (Innovations in Dementia, 2019; Seddon et al., 2023). This requires a sensitive understanding of how different groups of older adults can participate and a critical reflection with which intention they are involved in research, policy, and practice development.

Purpose and scope

Working Group One of the PAAR-net COST Action (CA 22167) looks at participatory approaches with older adults with needs of caring and support activities of daily living related to their health, well-being, and well-becoming while living at home, in care or nursing homes and other settings. Whilst group members have a broad range of expertise and interests, underpinning our work, and the content of this White Paper, is a vision of older adults as co-creators and active contributors. We focus on peoples' strengths and expertise, rather than on medical conditions, frailty, and other potential limiters. Our work across a broad range of health, care and support settings is informed by:

- ➔ A strengths-based approach that focuses on older adults and *sees the person and their strengths and their expertise* first and foremost.
- ➔ A commitment to harnessing the expertise in our local networks to overcome barriers to participation and involvement and nurture effective co-creative ways of working.

By working together and learning together with older adults we can take action together across health, care and support settings.

2

CHALLENGES AND SCOPE FOR IMPROVEMENT

The inclusive and meaningful involvement of older adults is recognised as critical to the delivery of impactful research with real world application across health, care and support settings. However, translating this commitment into practice presents challenges – as well as opportunities – for researchers, for research funding organisations and stakeholders, for older adults, and for policymakers and practitioners (James and Buffel, 2022; Jones et al., 2024). This section discusses the challenges, focusing on changing nomenclature, implementing language inclusivity, ensuring meaningful involvement and addressing power imbalances, overcoming structural barriers and a lack of funding opportunities, and maximising learning opportunities across countries.

2.1. Nomenclature and key concepts

Nomenclature is challenging. Participatory approaches, and terms such as co-creation, co-production, co-design, involvement, and engagement can have different meanings and implications for people and for organisations across the spectrum of academia, health, care and support settings (Wanka and Urbaniak, 2023). Terms are often used interchangeably to describe activities and older adults' contributions to research, policy, and practice development. Key terms such as quality of life, wellbeing, well-becoming, care and caregiving are also contested, and there is no consensus about how we measure these quantitatively or capture these qualitatively.

To foster truly participatory discussions, we have identified that establishing a shared understanding of key terminology is essential. Through collaborative dialogue, these terms have gradually emerged, allowing for clearer communication and mutual comprehension within the group. In the following section, we present these terms to reflect both: the broad foundation of PAAR-net and our shared values of respect, inclusiveness and participation.

I. Well-being and well-becoming

„Well-being” is a term used widely across various research disciplines and in policy and practice literature. Well-being is the balance point between an individual’s own resource pool and the challenges they face (Dodge et al., 2012). The WHO has championed the concept of well-being since the 1940s (Larsen, 2022). However, there is disagreement about how it should be measured, and well-being is often used interchangeably with terms like „happiness,” „resilience,” „health,” and „health-related quality of life”. There is agreement in the scientific literature that well-being relates to peoples’ social, emotional, intellectual, mental, and physical wellness (Dodge et al., 2012). Features that are identified as important in considering social, emotional, intellectual, mental, and physical wellbeing are based in the likes of relationships, community, respect, agency, autonomy, happiness, satisfaction, and a sense of being valued by others.

Contrastingly, the term „well-becoming” whilst not new is not routinely used in everyday language or research outside of the child development field (Edwards, 2022). According to Kane (2007), well-becoming can be thought of as our multitude of life-journeys toward meaning and purposefulness. Moving from solely focusing on a concept of well-being to concepts of well-being and well-becoming acknowledges the influence that socioeconomic and other local, national, and global conditions in a particular life-course stage have on subsequent life-course stages (Edwards, 2022).

Well-becoming has a future focus – for example, becoming well, staying well, and thriving, and it acknowledges both the opportunities and challenges for the future. By focusing on both well-being and well-becoming we get a better sense of what people want for their futures, what outcomes they aspire to, and what the barriers and facilitators to achieving these outcomes are.

II. Care and support

The concept of care is central to our social life and interpersonal relationships, and it encompasses a wide range of meanings that differ depending on the cultural, social and policy and practice settings. Due to the interdisciplinarity nature of the PAAR-net COST Action, we accept a broad approach to care as a form of meaningful work, social solidarity, as well as an expression of interpersonal relationships and a source of personal meaning that is often related to professional labour, family relations, and state policies (Fine 2007). This overarching approach encompasses specific practices related to providing health and welfare services and support (both paid and unpaid), social relationships, and supporting older adults in their local communities and in family settings (Bowers et al., 2001).

Research and policy typically distinguish between paid and unpaid carers (referred also as formal and informal carers). Paid professionals provide essential care and support to those older adults who need assistance with activities of daily living or support with specific medical needs. Smith et al. (2022) found that paid carers increasingly focus on promoting independence and quality of life, alongside meeting physical needs. This shift aligns with the active ageing paradigm, which sees older adults as capable and autonomous individuals. However, challenges persist, including person power shortages and the need for specialised training in care for older adults, as noted by Fulmer et al. (2021).

An unpaid carer can be understood as „anyone who cares, unpaid, for a friend or family member who due to illness, disability, a mental health problem or an addiction cannot cope without their support” (Carers Trust, 2019). Over 80% of adults in Europe who need long-term care and support are currently cared for by unpaid carers (Eurocarers, 2023). When thinking about care and support it is important to acknowledge the complexities and dynamics of caring relationships. Many older adults are not only receiving care and support for their needs but are themselves carers, usually for their spouses/partners, adult children who have a lifelong disability and for their grandchildren. A challenge for involving and engaging with unpaid carers is that not all individuals will identify with this label and instead will see their caring role as part of or an extension of a pre-existing relationship.

2.2. Language inclusivity and the challenge of stereotypes

An inclusive understanding of ageing is the basis for good communication with older adults and the scientific community. Ageing is a „normal“ human experience, and all forms of exclusion through ageism, including the use of inappropriate language, are unacceptable and must be combated. Most recently, the Covid-19 Pandemic has highlighted that the voices and experiences of older adults themselves are often not recognised by policymakers designing solutions to address the health and the wellbeing of older adults. Numerous resources (Ayalon, 2020; Fraser et al., 2020; Ehni and Wahl, 2020) emphasise that in the pandemic circumstances ageism was magnified. Researchers as traditional „stewards“ of the research processes feeding into policy and practice intervention designs have primary responsibility to challenge these societal and personal ageist assumptions, practices, and attitudes and the cornerstone of these efforts is the use of sensitive and unbiased language.

Inclusive, respectful, non-ageist language is crucial in participatory approaches to working with older adults that avoids the use of certain expressions or words that may be perceived as exclusionary or offensive, such as elderly or infirm (Appleby, 2022). All terms which connote a stereotype or suggest a fatalistic attitude, can be perceived as offensive. Insensitive phrases or those that imply prejudice should be avoided in everyday and professional language (see [Quick guide to avoid ageism in communication](#) by WHO, 2021).

In this sense, negative language includes terms like *seniors, elderly, the aged, ageing dependents, old-old, young-old, demented people or people suffering from dementia, geriatric*. These terms have no agreed-upon meaning and contribute to stigma. Also euphemisms like *people of a certain age* might suggest there is something shameful about ageing; or saying things such as „love” or „deary” to an older adult can be derogatory. For participatory activities to enable the full participation of older adults, we must see the older adults as individuals and address them by their names (Van Vleck, 2022; Morrison, 2023).

More neutral terms are now preferred both in research, policy, and practice (Van Vleck 2022, Morrison 2023):

- *older persons/people/adults/individuals/population*
- *persons 65 years and older*
- *people who are in a later stage of life*
- *people older in experience*
- *third and fourth age people*

The language used to describe older adults who have contact with health and care services is also problematic, especially the term „service user” which has common parlance across European countries. „Service user” is a challenging and impersonal label that prioritises services over people and has negative associations with illicit drug use. In a health, care and support research context, the term does not recognise the active contribution older adults make to research. It foregrounds only one aspect of a person’s life (i.e., contact with services due to challenges experienced in later life), and it fails to acknowledge the wider context of people’s lives and the wealth of experiential knowledge they bring.

While referring to the well-being of older adults, the concept of „successful ageing” is used quite often although considered by many as non-inclusive as it often prioritises certain ideals that fail to account for the diverse experiences of ageing (Waddell et al., 2024). For instance, the dominant model of successful ageing emphasises physical health, cognitive function and independence, which can marginalise people with disabilities or chronic conditions. In other words, the approach assumes the people can control such aspects of ageing, without considering social and environmental and genetic factors beyond their control (Katz and Calasanti, 2015). The idea of „successful ageing” also often reflects western, individualistic values such as autonomy and productivity, which may not coincide with other cultural perspectives that value community support and interdependence (Holstein and Minkler, 2003). Furthermore, the concept of successful ageing perpetuates ageism; it reinforces ageist stereotypes that equate ageing with decline or failure, unless unrealistic or specific standards of ageing are met (e.g., remaining active, looking youthful) (Lamb, 2014).

Consistent use of inclusive language that challenges ageist attitudes, practices, and systems is considered critical to the success of the participatory approaches among older adults (Mody et al., 2008). Even if the preferred terminology of inclusive language continues to evolve, its common use is crucial for combating ageism and its consequences. By choosing words and concepts that promote a respectful, positive attitude toward older adults and avoiding words that reflect implicit biases, we can help to change the prevailing negative narrative and to facilitate the successful involvement of older adults in research, policy and practice development (Laslett, 1994; Langmann and Weßel, 2023).

2.3. Transactional approaches, power imbalances, and lack of inclusivity

Research studies using participatory approaches with older adults typically lack inclusivity and neglect the heterogeneity of the older adult population (Poli et al., 2023; Urbaniak, 2023). Older adults from minority ethnic backgrounds are particularly likely to be excluded from research in general, and more concerted efforts need to be made to widen participatory approaches with these older adults in their community settings (Gilmore-Bykovskyi et al., 2022). Brown et al. (2014) described several barriers to the recruitment of adults from different ethnic communities for participation in mental health research, highlighting the importance of being culturally sensitive toward participants' language, religious beliefs, gender or possible stigma of illness, and the need for building trust through communication and cultural awareness among researchers and practitioners. Including older adults from ethnic minority and marginalised backgrounds in research and policy development helps researchers prioritise the voices and needs of these older individuals in real-life settings (Norris et al., 2007).

Challenges relating to intersectionality and interdisciplinarity need to be addressed if we are to successfully implement sensitive and inclusive approaches to working with older adults. The intersectionality may involve active focus on relationships between ageing and existing inequalities (income, education) or identity characteristics (minority background, abilities, religious beliefs or sex and gender), and takes into consideration that events and life conditions cannot be understood as shaped only by one factor but a complexity of relations (Collins and Bilge 2016). Gilmore-Bykovskyi et al. (2022) note that conventional practices often fail to recognize participation barriers (financial, transportation, linguistic, and/or logistical) that disproportionately burden participants from minority communities and the intersectional factors that underpin health inequalities in ageing.

Approaches to public involvement can be transactional and inflexible in nature. They often focus on the practicalities of scheduling traditional advisory group meetings and data gathering exercises rather than trying to develop more innovative and inclusive ways to engage. These approaches can be impersonal, and they can restrict opportunities for imaginative thinking. They can also leave people feeling disconnected from the research and practice development activities, inhibit the building of mutually supportive and trusting relationships over time and they can exacerbate power imbalances (Seddon et al., 2023). Power imbalances between academic researchers and older adults persist, with academic knowledge often being privileged over experiential knowledge (Ray, 2007).

2.4. Practice limitations and resource constraints

In trying to let the voices, wishes, and experiences of older adults be heard through participatory approaches we encounter barriers such as poor practice, and resource constraints. Several reviews of Patient and Public Involvement (henceforth PPI) in research have found low levels of involvement and poor-quality reporting (see Cook et al., 2019; Miah et al., 2019). Adding to this, difficulties related to issues such as tokenism and box-ticking, where PPI activities are carried out but do not translate in real change/do not lead to changes in practice, have also been reported.

Boylan et al. (2019) report that despite the increased interest in, and support for PPI in theory, researchers may feel both apprehensive and reluctant to change their practice, given other professional and institutional priorities as well as career development concerns. This form of tokenism as it relates to PPI occurs when the involvement of individuals remains superficial or symbolic, for example attendance at an advisory meeting, rather than meaningful and substantive. Ultimately, this can undermine the goals of PPI in research which seek to meaningfully incorporate the perspectives and contributions of the public into the research process (Lang et al., 2022).

While funding organisations increasingly recognize the importance of including older adults in research, there remains a scope for improvement and better guidance on how to budget for participatory activities into research. Participation is not a cost-neutral activity and it requires significant financial investment and time commitment for researchers and for older adults. As Urbaniak and Wanka point out, funding bodies rarely have mechanisms in place to allow for the study design to be co-created, and as a result the participatory approaches often remain outside the scope of many researcher activities (2023). It is important to note that informing policy and affecting positive change takes time. Therefore, it is imperative to share and manage people's expectations of research and be explicit about what can be achieved in terms of policy and practice development in a given time. This can help prevent failures to deliver on promised outcomes and support management of uncertainty or conflict in terms of delivery on agreed results (Involve, 2005).

Despite the increased commitment to support public involvement in research across health, care and support settings, the under-reporting of co-creative activities and the older adult public contributor perspective, in research outputs, is noted (Roberts et al, 2020; Georges et al., 2022). Looking to the future, it is vital to think about how best we can capture the positive difference *working together* and *learning together* makes for us all – for older adults, for researchers, and for policy makers and practitioners involved in the planning and delivery of treatment, care and support (Jones et al., 2024).

3

OPPORTUNITIES AND POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

3.1. National standards, guidelines, and toolkits

Some countries have taken steps to address the challenges described in the previous section. This includes the development of national standards and toolkits for involvement activities across health, care and support settings. For example, the **National Standards for Public Involvement in Research** (National Institute for Health Research [NIHR], 2019) seek to embed co-creative activity across health and social care research and improve the purpose, quality, and consistency of public involvement (NIHR, 2019). Six national standards showcase how effective public involvement in research requires:

- equal opportunities,
- collaboration to establish and sustain mutually respectful relationships,
- support and learning opportunities to build confidence and skills,
- timely and relevant communications,
- monitoring to capture the difference involvement has made,
- effective governance to support public contributors to manage, lead, and decide.

The **Public Involvement in Research Impact Toolkit (PIRIT)** was developed by the Wales Cancer Research Unit in 2023, and it is designed to help plan and integrate public involvement in research, to profile public contributions and the difference they make to the research in health, care and support settings and to report impact against the UK Standards for Public Involvement. The pragmatic tools are intended to be co-owned by researchers and public contributors to facilitate discussion, collaborative working, and a clear approach to public involvement activities and impact reporting.

Similar to the UK and other countries, in the Irish context, policies as they relate to PPI and overall service development have been in place for several years. Despite the [PPI Ignite Network](#) being central to the development of PPI across the country, as Gilfoyle et al. (2022) note, as a normalised way of researching, PPI is still in its formative days in Ireland. Building on the initial PPI Ignite Programme (2017-2021), the 2020 Ignite Network seeks to promote excellence and inspire innovation in PPI in health and social care research across Ireland (PPI Ignite Network, 2024). Adding to these aforementioned developments, there have been efforts to set up a partnership-focused framework that will guide the recruitment and establishment of a PPI panel of older adults, family carers and academic researchers (Conneely et al., 2020).

Practical resources have been published to help researchers engage with specific groups of older adults, including those who are often marginalised, such as people living with dementia. See, for example, the Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project, which has published [good practice guidance](#) (DEEP, 2013). Other resources include national guidelines from important local NGOs on the use of inclusive approaches that are both culturally and linguistically sensitive to the experiences of older adults in various settings (Czechia: MILA, 2023). These materials are based on participatory approaches within the health and care environment, conducted by different stakeholders and organisations, and can also serve as a basis for implementing participatory approaches in other research and policy designs.

3.2. Project examples: Enhancing inclusion, empowerment, and decision-making

Throughout Europe projects are emerging which focus on ensuring diversity and inclusion through citizenship programmes aimed at socially excluded older adults, such as the EU-Project „RE:Dialogue” (2013-2014) or the research project „Socially Excluded Older Adults: Voices and Experiences” (SEVEN) in Austria and other countries in the EU. By implementing methods such as the role of a mediator who is chairing a village group of older adults, holding group discussions or writing an auto-ethnography, the projects were able to capture the main points of challenge in accessing services, care and support for the wellbeing of older adults. Moreover, they also facilitated the forging of meaningful and respectful relationships between older adults as co-creators in the communities and in the project teams.

The inclusion of writing activities as participatory approaches are not the only methods to support engagement of older adults in research and policy designs. For example, Smith and Phillipson (2021) involved older adults living with late-stage dementia in a residential care facility in Australia directly through innovative methods of journey and body mapping and the development of transitional objects (scarves and blankets). The study aimed to understand what helped the residents feel „at home” and what was associated with a „good day” and quality of life. Another international research project based in the UK investigated through creative and arts-based approaches what neighbourhoods mean for people living with dementia and how individuals can be supported to remain socially and physically active (Campbell and Clark, 2023). People living with dementia were involved at various stages of the research through walking interviews, participatory social network mapping, home tours, and the co-development of graphic „magazines”. The use of innovative and creative methods in participatory approaches provides new ways to engage older adults with various care and support needs in research, policy, and practice development, supporting their well-being through understanding more about the things that are significant and meaningful to them (Smith and Phillipson, 2021).

INVOLVE, the United Kingdom’s public participation charity emphasises the importance of research that is conducted with or by members of the public, and they highlight the need for collaboration and reflection across the research life cycle with experts who have living experience. As well as the benefits for the research, there are also transformative benefits for members of the public themselves, including older adults who welcome the opportunity to learn new skills, build confidence and meet new people (Bieńko et al. 2023). This is evidenced in recent work reflecting on the involvement of people living with dementia in research about building resilience (Seddon et al., 2023), which highlights the sense of fulfilment people feel in contributing to research about health, care and support that has the potential to affect positive changes in peoples’ quality of life, both now and in the future.

Apart from research projects and their published resources and guidelines, there are many programmes and practices in place around Europe and beyond utilising participatory approaches and methods to enhance wellbeing, care and support for older adults. The PAAR-net COST Action (CA22167) aims to address these practices with older co-creators, local policy makers, social and health-care workers and unpaid carers through discussions, knowledge exchange events in local languages, sharing experiences across countries and settings. Some programmes and practices provide opportunities for older adults to collaborate and meet with one another and share their living experiences.

These involve, for example, therapeutic gardening and horticultural therapy in which older adults both design the jointly shared space, co-work in gardening activities, participate in workshops and leisurely enjoy the garden (Turkey: Kabakçı, 2023; Italy: Pedrinolla et al., 2019). These practices promote physical activity and social engagement which are considered to be vital for healthy ageing (Gough et al., 2021; Sebastião et al., 2014). Participatory approaches also play an important role in making technologies available for older adults to improve their well-being and access to care and support. For example, Noordman et al. (2017) utilised participatory approaches with older adults to develop tools to help older cancer patients to better prepare for their encounters with nurses and physicians. Span et al. (2017) co-developed an interactive web tool DecideGuide for shared decision-making with people living with dementia (for more on the interplay between technology and participatory approaches, please access PAAR-net WG3 white paper).

Other programmes and projects focus on addressing well-being, well-becoming, care and support within the environmental and cultural settings in which older adults live. Special attention is often paid to the involvement of older adults in decision-making processes within their communities and establishing advisory boards representing the older adults in local governments. For example, in Turkish villages and towns, local decision-making processes include the formation of „ihtiyar meclisi” (*elder councils*). The council convenes at least once a week and prioritises village affairs, decides on communal labour and the distribution of produce, oversees expenditures of the village headman, approves the village budget, and mediates disputes.

These practices can be difficult to implement in different cultural settings. Based on her experience in Zambian villages Charlotte Gruber notes that the main success factor of the whole programme she was part of, was to think carefully about working together with people. It was important to work closely with the village population, involve them in all decisions, build up their expertise in recognising problems and finding solutions together. Implementing diverse and culturally sensitive approaches is crucial for effectively supporting the well-being and well-becoming of older adults in practice (for more on the interplay between community, place and participatory approaches, please access PAAR-net WG2 white paper.

3.3. Inclusive approaches and methods in PAAR

Innovative approaches that bring together older adults, researchers, policy and practice developers are beginning to emerge. One such approach is the [Social Care Innovation Labs](#) (#SCIL) initiative, bringing people with a diverse range of professional and living experience together to co-create research, policy, and practice development ideas. The ethos underpinning #SCIL centres on the need to work together to focus on the complex social situations that older adults experience and seek to find real solutions. The labs act as a connecting hub and provide a safe space to discuss ideas. Delivered through the Centre for Ageing and Dementia Research and the Developing Evidence Enriched Practice programme in the UK, #SCILs are underpinned by three core principles, namely, meaningfully involving, innovating, and improving (Seddon et al., 2021). #SCILs have supported successful research grant capture (Toms et al., 2020) and ongoing research projects as an innovative and participatory approach to data collection (Alexander et al., 2023; Toms et al., 2023). In Ireland, similar aims have been followed by research [CO-AGE](#) developing a co-operative model to empower older adults, family carers and professional care workers to co-create high-quality home care within a relational framework. The model created an opportunity for older adults and their families to shape the design and delivery of services, thereby empowering care recipients and improving their experience (Power and Crowley, 2024).

In recent decades, critical and alternative approaches such as age narratives have significantly increased in popularity, exploring themes of identity, memory, love, well-being, and the complexity of experiences. Personal accounts of ageing act as „roadmaps,” which may help carers anticipate and better navigate care-related challenges (Fredman, 2016). Narratives offer significant insights into unique and collective ageing experiences and highlight the nuances among older adults (Casado Gual et al., 2016; Falcus et al., 2023). According to age scholar Anne Wyatt-Brown, „[o]nly by combining research with novels and memoirs can we begin to comprehend the varieties of ageing experience in our time” (2010: 57). In the life writing framework, revised diary methods, memoirs, personal accounts and solicited diaries are increasingly utilised as a way to capture lived experiences, giving older adults time to reflect about feelings and experiences lived in an environment without the inference of a researcher (Vořanská, 2017; Roos, 2023). A Swedish study by Lorenzini and Persson (2023) used solicited diaries with photo elicitation to highlight narrating of older adults with home-care needs about their daily self-care routines to help co-design their home care products and promote good health and well-being.

The inclusion of writing activities as participatory approaches are not the only methods to support engagement of older adults in research and policy designs. For example, Smith and Phillipson (2021) involved older adults living with late-stage dementia in a residential care facility in Australia directly through innovative methods of journey and body mapping and the development of transitional objects (scarves and blankets). The study aimed to understand what helped the residents feel „at home” and what was associated with a „good day” and quality of life. Another international research project based in the UK investigated through creative and arts-based approaches what neighbourhoods mean for people living with dementia and how individuals can be supported to remain socially and physically active (Campbell and Clark, 2023). People living with dementia were involved at various stages of the research through walking interviews, participatory social network mapping, home tours, and the co-development of graphic „magazines”. The use of innovative and creative methods in participatory approaches provides new ways to engage older adults with various care and support needs in research, policy, and practice development, supporting their well-being through understanding more about the things that are significant and meaningful to them (Smith and Phillipson, 2021).

3.4. Training and skills development

Public involvement in research is often criticised for being tokenistic in nature (Beresford, 2019). Especially while PPI is increasingly expected across funding organisations in Europe, a risk is rising of participatory methods becoming a tick box exercise. There is an urgent need to address this and to embed participatory approaches to working with older adults into mainstream research training. Actively engaging with older adults and co-creating research and practice development takes skill, and it is important that these skills are clearly articulated through training, and through continuing professional development opportunities. This includes researcher training to develop meaningful connections and shared values, enable people to define and choose how they engage, and communicate in an accessible, open, and transparent way. Academic researchers are accustomed to writing scientifically, however, scientific jargon and complex methodologies can inhibit engagement with research. In this context, modules specific to participatory methods and techniques for communicating with older adults should be added to the training programs for academic researchers in order to work with older adults in a more meaningful and effective way (Blair and Minkler, 2009). It is also recommended that these trainings should be designed to help researchers develop a deeper understanding of the needs and expectations of older adults and use more accessible and understandable language rather than complex scientific jargon. In this way, older adults can be engaged more effectively and meaningfully in research processes and be encouraged to become truly inclusive and interactive.

Equally important is training for older adults who want to become co-creators and ambassadors for research. A crucial consideration is the availability and delivery of public training, which can include an introduction to research, strategies for building confidence, and inspiring people to engage with research and to meet with their peers. Therefore, establishing volunteering or mentorship programmes is crucial for ensuring participatory approaches where older adults can pass on their knowledge and experiences.

3.5. Building networks and evidencing results

Ensuring the impact of participatory approaches is essential to supporting sustainable research, care, and policy networks that can translate the voices of older co-creators into practice. Preconditions for creating the networks are often adequate and long-term funding opportunities, improved communication, and interdisciplinary partnership. In a similar way to the [Social Care Innovation Labs \(#SCIL\)](#) initiative, one of the models for a sustainable and successful interdisciplinary collaboration between scientists, care providers and educators in long-term care is the [Living Lab in Ageing and Long-Term Care](#) managed under Maastricht University in the Netherlands. The Living Lab is presented not just as a physical space, but mostly as a network in which „researchers collaborate through continuous discussion with older adults and their families, client representatives, professionals, health care directors, policy makers, and teachers” (Verbeek et al., 2020). At the centre of the Living Lab idea is a structural multidisciplinary collaboration between research, policy, education and practice which is based on interdisciplinarity and, most importantly, joint appointments of senior researchers working at both the university and long-term care organisations (e.g. nursing homes, assisted and group living facilities). Through innovative small-scale, homelike care environments, green care farms and workplaces of practice-based Linking Pins, the lab aims to develop, evaluate and implement interventions improving quality of life and care in nursing homes (Verbeek et al., 2020).

The concept of interdisciplinary networks utilising participatory approaches, while addressing well-being, well-becoming, care and support, is gaining traction (Verloo et al., 2021). For example, in March 2024 the [North West Coast Living Lab in Ageing and Dementia](#) was launched at the University of Liverpool, based on the Living Lab in the Netherlands, with the aim to foster further collaboration between academics in dementia research and social care and support service providers (such as day care centres, home care agencies, and care homes).

Building networks across policy, research, older adults, third sector organisations and relevant stakeholders is vital if participatory approaches are to have scientific and societal impact. Along with networking activities, evidencing participatory approaches and methods more effectively both in published outputs and policy and practice workshops and discussions should be at the centre of our activities. Describing and sharing experiences with implementation of participatory approaches in research, policy design, and practice and being explicit about the difference participation has made, creates a pool of knowledge from which we all can learn and be inspired. Such practices will promote the living experience of older adults and put participatory approaches at the forefront of the future research and policy-making where it can make a difference.

CASE STUDIES: EXAMPLES OF PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES

This section showcases a variety of case studies developed in diverse settings. Each has been included in this white paper to illustrate the wide-ranging approaches within PAAR-net, highlighting the richness of perspectives and experiences represented. Due to space constraints, these examples represent just a fraction of the ongoing work within the network.

Case Study 1 – Co-designing with people living with dementia: insights from the IDoService project to support participation in meaningful activities

Isabelle Tournier¹ & Kristina Niedderer²

¹ Univ Paul Valery Montpellier 3 (France)

² Manchester Metropolitan University (UK)

Introduction

The EU funded IDoService (2020-2022) project aimed to address the difficulty often reported by people living with mild to moderate dementia to actively participate in meaningful activities (Innes et al., 2016; Ziebuhr et al., 2023). In consequence, the project targeted to co-develop a user-friendly service for people living with mild to moderate dementia to realise themselves and contribute to society. The starting idea was for the service to support people to plan, connect with and participate in tailored opportunities.

¹Acknowledgements: The IDoService project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 895620. We also would like to thank all participants in the project for their invaluable input and advice.

Design and Methods

The research team, composed of researchers in psychology of ageing and design for health, followed a service design approach that corresponds to a holistic, co-creative approach to improve the quality of service provision (Stickdorn and Schneider, 2011). The project relied on co-design to involve various relevant stakeholders (people living with dementia, familial and professional care partners, as well as staff from age-related or activity-related organisations in Greater Manchester, UK).

The project was organised in three successive steps. The first step (Step 1) was interviews and focus groups to learn more about preferences, barriers, and facilitators to participation in meaningful activities while living with dementia in Greater Manchester. The second step was to co-design workshops to work together with stakeholders to reflect on data from interviews in step 1 to prototype potential relevant tools. Based on these various inputs, the research team designed the I Can Do Pathway toolkit as the new service and outcome of the IDoService project. The co-design prototype was refined and tested in the last step (Step 3) and can be found online for free at www.idoservice.org. A total of 61 stakeholders took part in at least one of these three steps:

- 15 people living with mild to moderate dementia,
- 15 familial and 3 professional care partners,
- 28 staff from age-related or activity-related organisations.

Implementation

The project encountered several challenges to involve experts by experience during this research (i.e., people living with dementia and their caregivers), in part due to the Covid-19 pandemic situation at the time of the project which started in October 2020. The first months of the project were marked by a strict lockdown in the UK, service providers only offering online activities to people, and we had to make some adjustments of the initially planned project. Firstly, we had to switch from in-person interviews and focus groups to largely online delivery (i.e., Microsoft Teams professional account). We originally planned to have interviews and focus groups with all categories of stakeholders. However, we estimated that an online format for the focus groups might be not suitable or comfortable for people living with dementia due to the supplementary cognitive load and fatigue due to online meetings, especially with several people. In consequence, we decided to finally not organise focus groups with them but only some individual interviews when it was possible again when following all the sanitary safety rules.

Beyond the limitations due to the Covid-19 context, other adaptations had to be done regarding the research material to make it accessible to people living with dementia, who might have additional impairments besides cognitive ones. Adaptations included research activities themselves, but also ethics forms, recruitment flyers, and deliverables. A significant challenge was making documents informative enough but still easy to understand, especially for people who never participated in research activities before. Regarding ethics and the consent process for the IDoService project, all participants were informed in advance about the research activity to decide if they wished to participate or not. Information and consent forms were provided at least one week in advance to give them enough time to read through and their consent was re-confirmed on the day.

Besides using plain English and short sentences, an effort was made to use fonts big enough, sans-serif, with attractive colours and sufficient contrasts between the different parts of the document. As mobility can be an issue for older adults, especially for those living with dementia that often cannot drive anymore or take public transport, we offered transportation by a research partner or covered taxi costs to ensure they could comfortably attend the research venue. Participants were also encouraged to come along with a relative if it would make them feel more confident and at ease. A growing number of guidelines are now available to help researchers make their work more accessible (e.g., Deep website – The UK network of dementia voices; Denning et al., 2020; Litherland and Hare, 2024). Finally, one very important point stressed by the groups we were working with and has been previously involved in participatory research was the need to ensure continuity of communication and to keep co-designer participants informed of the outcomes and further developments to ensure they feel that their input is being valued.

Benefits and opportunities

One of the benefits of the participatory approach in this project was to learn more and discuss how the service to be designed should revolve around the gap between memory assessment services and access to social activities and how it might build on and complement existing dementia care and wellbeing plans. Bringing together stakeholders from the different boroughs of Greater Manchester (i.e., 2.8 million residents) allowed us to truly understand the local context, with the existing service landscape, including some of the strengths as well as disparities in the existing service offer.

We discussed together the current and potential roles of GPs, social prescribers and dementia advisors in informing people about activities and linking them with suitable services as part of the IDoService. We also discussed which format the service should take to embrace and adapt to the diverse interests and needs of people through linking with volunteers' organisation programmes and the opportunities and potential challenges related. Insights from the interviews and workshops have enabled developing the concept for the volunteer service for people with dementia as well as the format of wellbeing mentor sessions to support it. During the co-design process, the initial concept evolved from a standalone service to one that seamlessly integrates into the existing service landscape, utilising current resources and expertise to provide the service. Collaborating with community stakeholders in a participatory approach resulted in a concrete service concept with a well-defined path to implementation, advocating in favour of co-design (Niedderer et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Developed through a co-design approach involving various stakeholders, the I Can Do pathway is a volunteer service for people living with dementia to support them with staying connected with their community, finding a purpose and meaning in their everyday lives, and feeling valued following the diagnosis (Tournier et al., 2022). It explores people's strengths and interests; allows them to meet volunteer service representatives to find out what is on offer locally and to discuss interests with peers; and to work out details for realising the interests identified with their wellbeing mentor, care partner and volunteer services representative.

Case Study 2 – Experiences from Participatory Research in Serbia: Exploring Elder Abuse

Bojana Matejic

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Belgrade (Serbia)

Introduction

The global population ageing has contributed to a concerning rise in elder abuse (abuse of older adults). Older women, in particular, face a greater risk of abuse, but this public health issue is often ignored and mainly invisible in many societies (Crockett, Brandl, and Dabby, 2015). According to the latest available data, in Serbia, 16% of older women aged 65 to 74 experienced some form of violence after reaching the age of 65 (Todorovic et al., 2020). This study aimed to assess the social norms and cultural attitudes toward older persons, to explore the range of attitudes and behaviours which are tolerated in society but represent violence and abuse, to explore the characteristics and impact of gender-based violence against older women, along with the degree to which various institutions respond to this issue and how the complex societal systems respond to their needs.

Design and methods

The project, „Empowerment of Older Women: Prevention of Violence through Changing Social Norms in Serbia (EmPreV)”, supported by the European Union and Austrian Development Agency, consisted of qualitative and quantitative research phases (Todorovic et al., 2021). The participatory research approach was applied during the qualitative phase of the study. Engaging older volunteers from the network of the Red Cross in research offered firsthand experience and insights into elder abuse issues within the community. They were engaged during pre-focus group planning, recruiting participants, connecting with the Roma communities, designing the structured guide for focus group discussion and case study for initiating the discussion, and during discussions and post-focus group analysis. Our research included 157 respondents participating in 17 focus groups across four regions in Serbia, from four cities and two villages. The focus groups included women from three age categories.

Implementation

We have engaged our non-academic partners in all practical steps of conducting our research, from the planning phases to recruiting participants and organising focus group discussions. Initiating discussions on sensitive topics like elder abuse can be challenging; therefore, a real-life case study, prepared in the interaction with our volunteers and presented at the outset of the focus group, facilitated engagement and open dialogue with the participants. This approach encouraged open dialogue and empathy, offering a more comprehensive perspective of the complex issue of elder abuse. Sharing genuine experiences added authenticity to our research, ensuring that the discussion reflected the realities faced by older adults. A real-life story captivated the participants' attention, fostering more engaging and interactive focus group discussions beneficial to all parties involved, yielding insights on a topic of study for researchers, and providing actionable and empowering information for participants.

Benefits and Opportunities

Violence against older adults is a sensitive topic. The participatory approach gave the well-designed research framework an additional quality to the research process, as pointed out in recently published literature (Urbaniak and Wanka, 2023; Messelis and Vanoutrive, 2023). By participating in our research, our non-academic partners contributed ideas and initiatives to establish support mechanisms in local communities, including initiatives such as SOS telephone lines and the establishment of clubs and daycare centres for older people. They suggested utilising socially responsible media content and educational systems to promote positive family values, foster good neighbourly relations, raise awareness about intergenerational solidarity, and address the issue of elder abuse. Also, our volunteers encouraged older women's active participation in the local community through engagement in associations, organisations, volunteering, and other forms of involvement.

Conclusion

In future efforts to address elder abuse, it is essential to educate older women about the various forms of violence and risk factors, provide psychosocial support, ensure professionals receive ongoing training on the specific nature of abuse against older women, and enhance coordination among relevant local stakeholders to strengthen system responses. Evidence-based policies are crucial, and the participation of community volunteers as non-academic research partners is the practice that can support and upgrade these intentions.

Case Study 3 – Effectiveness of INOSEL Program, Consisting of Integrative Nursing and Omaha System for Older Women Feeling Loneliness: a Randomized Controlled Trial

Ayşegül Ilgaz & Sebahat Gözüm

Akdeniz University, Faculty of Nursing (Türkiye)

Introduction

Loneliness is a critical factor affecting the health and well-being of older adults. In Europe, the prevalence of loneliness in the ageing population varies between 5 and 70% in individual countries (Doman and le Roux, 2010; Dahlberg and McKee, 2014). Loneliness is also a gendered phenomenon, being 1.4 times more common amongst older women than men (Anil, Pratasad, and Puttaswamy, 2016), with one of the factors being women's higher longevity (Dahlberg and McKee, 2014). Some studies suggest that older adults' experiences of loneliness reduce their quality of life and may contribute to many health problems, such as hypertension, coronary heart disease, stroke, depression, dementia and Alzheimer's disease (NASEM, 2020; Donovan and Blazer, 2020). Caring about meeting the needs of older adults in terms of the quality and quantity of their social relations is therefore critical for their healthy ageing.

Group-based programmes in the forms of physical activity, cinema and theatre visits, sightseeing, and person-centred workshops are among the opportunities for enhancing social interactions (Landeiro et al., 2017; Kang, Park, and Wallace, 2018). However, more holistic approaches to loneliness are often needed to offer more sensitive and participatory care, such as the Integrative Nursing (IN) health approach that considers the individual, family and society together with the patient's environment and relationships. According to IN, programmes that address older adults' environment, support existing healing processes, allow participants to benefit from the healing effect of nature, prioritise person-centred care, and strengthen already established relationships (Koithan, 2014).

In our study, we combined the Integrative Nursing (IN) principles and the Omaha System (OS) – INOSEL (Integrative Nursing and Omaha System for older women who feel Loneliness) program – to evaluate their effect on the physical, mental, social and spiritual health of community-dwelling older women experiencing a high level of loneliness. [The Omaha System](#) is a research-based comprehensive practice and documentation standardised taxonomy designed to describe client care. This system aims to support collaborative efforts between researchers and social and healthcare practitioners to ensure better integration of research, practice, and education. According to our hypotheses, when compared with the control group, participants in the INOSEL program would show (a) a lower loneliness level (low level), (b) a higher physical activity level, (c) better health status perception, (d) greater social support perception, (e) better social inclusion perception, (f) greater well-being perception and (g) higher spirituality perception.

Design and methods

The study was a randomised controlled trial with parallel groups without participant blinding, examining the effect of the 12-week INOSEL program combining IN and the OS. The study involved 69 older women who experienced loneliness. The first step determined the loneliness level of older women who applied to a Family Health Center (FHC). In the second step, older women feeling loneliness were randomised to the INOSEL and control groups and underwent 12-week INOSEL programs. These programmes aim to improve older women's physical, mental, social, and spiritual health and enhance their social networks through walking, picnics, sightseeing, cinema, theatre, and group training sessions (on healthy nutrition, stress management, and interpersonal relations).

Implementation: person-centred programmes

Each participant's health problems were determined according to the OS Problem Classification Scheme. The most common health issues identified were insufficient social interaction, interpersonal relationships, physical activity, nutrition, issues with circulatory and intestinal functions, sleep and rest patterns, and pain. 52.2% of the participants had at least one health problem in the psychosocial area, whilst the physiological and health behaviour numbers were 50.8% and 46.4%, respectively. Programmes were chosen from the OS Nursing Intervention Scheme according to the individual problem defined by the researchers in the Problem Classification Scheme. A total of 5008 interventions were applied to participants, and 50% of the interventions were focused on health education, guidance and counselling, 27.2% surveillance, 19.4% case management and 3.5% treatment and procedures.

Interaction, support group and support system interventions were mostly used for social interaction enhancement; exercises, interaction, support system, support group and stress management interventions for strengthening interpersonal relationships; and exercises, support system, and support group interventions for enhancing physical activity. Relaxation/breathing techniques, physical therapy, and medical and nursing care interventions were applied for pain issues; medication action/side effects, signs/symptoms, medical and nursing care interventions for circulatory function; dietary management, bowel care, medical and nursing care, medication action/side effects, signs/symptoms—physical interventions for bowel function; rest/sleep, medical and nursing care interventions for sleep and rest issues.

Benefits and opportunities

The project aimed to connect both researchers, older adults, as well as policy makers and practitioners. Many group activities were, therefore, conducted with the support of local governments (municipalities) and public institutions. Older women identified the barriers to participation in the programmes as poor access to transportation options or sudden onset of ill health. For that reason, the municipality provided transportation, food, and support personnel to ensure participation in group activities such as cinema, theatre, picnic, and environmental tours. The local cultural centre in the region also provided free entrance to cinemas and theatres and did not charge hall rents. The onset of ill health and exclusion of the participants made planning for activities challenging. Since the older women did not have group phone applications (such as WhatsApp), each had to be called individually. At the beginning of each week, the older women were contacted by phone to remind them of the activities to be held in the following days. Family members or neighbours of the participants could accompany them in the group activities.

Older women were first introduced to each other in the Family Health Center, which was chosen as the meeting point. Thus, the activities and awareness in the communities regarding the health of older women have also increased. Participation of older women in group activities such as picnics, trips, and theatre visits often resulted in forming friendship groups. Detecting women who felt lonely was also useful for local governments in showing the groups they needed support.

Conclusion

This study applied group-based and person-centred programmes based on IN principles, a practical application of holistic philosophy. The research found IN principles highly effective in lessening feelings of loneliness of older women living in the community by creating a framework for „a way of being-knowing-doing care”. The study demonstrated that OS could be used to record these programmes and provide visibility. Lastly, the findings confirmed all of the study hypotheses. INOSEL program reduced older women’s feelings of loneliness and positively affected their physical, mental, social and spiritual health. Combining IN and the OS provided a theoretical conceptual framework for planning older adults’ care in public and mental health services while using group and individual discussions to determine their needs. Recommendations based on the study findings include planning activities such as group-based walking, picnics, travel, theatre and cinema visits to reduce older adults’ loneliness and improve their health and well-being.

CONCLUSION

This White Paper has reflected on the diverse experiences of researchers, stakeholders, and older adults who are using participatory approaches with older adults to support research, policy, and practice development in health, care and support. Diversity in cultural, academic, professional, and personal backgrounds were highlighted. We have together identified the major barriers and facilitators in implementing participatory approaches with older adults in research, policy, and practice development, and suggested potential solutions, opportunities, and areas for improvement.

PAAR-net COST Action (CA22167) provides an excellent opportunity to take this work forward with policy-makers and stakeholders to:

- Embrace diversity and explore ways to harness the diversity of older adults' knowledge and living experiences for research, policy, and practice development.
- Actively support older adults as public contributors, academics, policy-makers and practitioners in good practice collaborations across health, care and support settings.
- Develop the capacity of older adult public contributors to become involved in research, policy, and practice development activities.
- Promote a research culture meaningfully influenced by older adult public contributors.

Whilst there is a general commitment across European countries to actively involve older adults in research, policy, and practice development, participatory approaches are still more established in some countries than others. Through our PAAR-net COST Action (CA22167) activities, we aim to bridge the gap between countries, practice disciplines and academic fields by:

- Co-creating shared standards for implementing participatory approaches in research focused on health, care and support of older adults.
- Collating good practice examples in participatory approaches to research, policy, and practice to encourage mutual learning across cultural, social, and geographical contexts.
- Co-developing, with older co-creators, materials and toolkits for researchers, practitioners, and policy-makers to make the voices of older adults visible in inclusive research, policy, and practice development.
- Making materials available in local languages and alternative formats (e.g., visuals) to bridge the gap between countries and between communities of older adults.
- Developing a network of researchers, stakeholders, practitioners, and older co-creators to enhance collaboration activities.

This White Paper provides a sound platform from which to take our activities forward, as we seek to *work with* and *learn with* older adults, deliver impactful research with real world application, and, ultimately, affect positive changes across health, care and support provision.

ADDITIONAL READING AND INFORMATION

Projects and centres implementing participatory approaches with older adults across health, care and support setting

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- *Competence Centre Participatory Health Care*. (2024). Bern University of Applied Sciences. <https://www.bfh.ch/en/research/research-areas/competence-centre-participatory-health-care/>

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